

Does Literacy influence Socio-cultural Determinants of Female Gender Mutilation? A Community Study in Southern Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Background: The practice of FGM is heavily predicated on its socio-cultural determinants which could be influenced by the extent of female literacy.

Objective: To explore the effect of female literacy on the socio-cultural determinants of Female Gender Mutilation in Akwa Ibom State, Southern Nigeria.

Methodology: This is a community based cross sectional survey conducted between June 2015 and December 2016 among 1452 women randomly selected using a proportionate stratified random sampling method from twelve communities distributed across Akwa Ibom State. They were interviewed using a structured interviewer-assisted questionnaire after signing an informed consent and was analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences, version 21.

Results: On bivariate association there was significant association between the level of literacy and socio-cultural determinants of FGM explored in this study. However, multivariable analysis showed significant associations between – primary level of education and the notion that FGM is a 'rite of passage' into womanhood [99%CI ; AOR= 6.12 (5.07- 6.88); p value <0.0001]; primary level of education and the notion that FGM enhances fertility [99%CI; AOR=3.36 (2.51- 4.46); P value<0.001]; primary [99%CI; AOR = 4.87(2.23 – 6.33); p<0.0001] and secondary level of education [99%CI; AOR=1.16(0.86 -1.89); p value< 0.01] and the belief that FGM bridles promiscuity.

Conclusion: Level of female literacy is positively related to socio-cultural determinants of FGM.

Keywords: female gender mutilation, female literacy

INTRODUCTION

The majority of Female Genital Mutilation (FGM) is the partial or total removal of the external female genitalia or other injury to the female genital organs whether for cultural, religious or other non-medical reasons¹. It involves the removal of the clitoral hood and clitoral glans; removal of the inner labia; and removal of the inner and outer labia and closure of the vulva ([infibulation](#))².

FGM is practiced in Africa, the Middle East, Indonesia and Malaysia, and by some migrants in Europe, United States and Australia. The practice of FGM is widespread in African countries but most common in North East Africa. About 200 million women and girls worldwide have undergone FGM³.

The practice of FGM is firmly grounded in socio-cultural beliefs. FGM is seen as a practice that distinguishes the male from female gender⁴. There is the belief that female genitalia are unsightly and dirty⁵ hence the need for its removal. FGM is also said to increase sexual pleasure for the potential male husband⁶. Women who have not undergone

FGM are believed to be unclean and are ostracized from their family⁷.

FGM, especially infibulation is believed to reduce sexual desire especially regarding premarital sex thereby preserving a girl's virginity. Virginity in these societies is seen as a symbol of purity and innocence⁸. FGM is also believed to enhance fertility in women in these societies⁹. Finally, FGM is seen as a necessary rite of passage into womanhood¹⁰.

Female genital mutilation has no health benefit and is associated with profound reproductive health morbidities and mortality¹¹. Women, who had undergone FGM, have significantly increased risks for adverse events during childbirth, and negative effects on their newborn babies².

The practice of FGM has been associated with a myriad of complications^{12,13}. These complications could be classified as acute and chronic⁴. Acute complications include severe pain, fatal haemorrhage, sepsis, tetanus, shock,

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urinary retention, genital ulcers and death^{12,13,14}. Chronic complications include epidermis cysts and abscesses, keloids, neuroma, fistulae, urinary incontinence, sexual dysfunction, infertility, prolonged obstructed labour and higher rate of episiotomy and caesarean sections^{15,16,17}. There is also emotional and psychological trauma¹⁷.

In the light of the effects of FGM and its accompanying mortality and morbidity, efforts have been made to eradicate the practice of FGM globally¹⁸. It has been suggested that increasing the rate and level of female literacy will help to eradicate FGM¹⁹. Female education has increased

dramatically in Nigeria over the years but FGM eradication rates in rural communities have not improved significantly²⁰. The question remains – does female literacy affect the socio-cultural determinants of FGM?

Objectives

> To examine the socio-cultural determinants of Female Gender Mutilation in rural communities in Akwa Ibom State, Southern Nigeria.

> To explore the effect of female literacy on the socio-determinants of Female Gender Mutilation in Akwa Ibom State, Southern Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

Study Location

Akwa Ibom State is a state in Nigeria located on the southern part of the country lying between latitudes 4°32'N and 5°33'N, and longitudes 7°25'E and 8°25'E with a population of over 5 million people.

Study Design

This is a community based cross sectional survey conducted between June 2015 and December 2016 among women in Akwa Ibom State. Ethical approval was received from the Ethical Review Board of Akwa Ibom State Ministry of Health.

Sample

1,452 women were randomly selected using a proportionate stratified random sampling method from twelve communities distributed across Akwa Ibom State. The population was stratified on the basis of senatorial district into Uyo, Eket and Ikot Ekpene. 4 local government areas were selected from each of the senatorial district by simple random balloting. A rural community was selected from each of the 4 local government areas by purposive sampling on the basis of current practice of FGM.

Respondents who were unwilling and/or unable to provide an informed consent were excluded. Respondents under 18 years of age were also excluded.

Study Instrument

The questionnaire was developed after a thorough literature review and further evaluation by experts in public health to ensure quality and content validity. The reliability of the instrument was determined through a test-retest reliability method with women in Uyo Metropolis. The

Pearson moment coefficient (r) was calculated. The coefficient 0.87 was determined.

They were interviewed using a structured interviewer-assisted questionnaire after signing an informed consent.

Measure

Participants completed study instrument assessing socio-demographic data, level of education (independent variable) and socio-cultural determinants of female gender mutilation (dependent variable). Level of literacy was determined as primary, secondary and tertiary. Covariates included age, marital status, religion, occupation, and average monthly income.

Analysis

The questionnaires were carefully examined for correctness and completeness, coded and analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23 for Windows. Quantitative data generated from the study was presented in form of tables and analyzed as descriptive frequencies and percentages.

Pearson's chi-square (X^2) was used to determine whether respondents in each level of literacy group differed significantly on the socio-cultural determinants of FGM. Logistic regression was used to examine association between level of literacy and socio-cultural determinants of FGM. Appropriate diagnostics to ensure that the data satisfied the proportional-odds assumption, necessary to conduct the logistic regression, was done.

P-value of less than 0.01 was accepted to be statistically significant.

RESULTS

A. Socio-demographic characteristic of Respondents

Majority of the respondents were in the 15-24 age group. The mean age group was 35-44 years. Most of the respondents were married (44.6%) while 38.2% were single. Most of the respondents were Christians

(83.2%), while the rest were traditional worshippers. Most of the respondents were self-employed (37.6%). Most of the respondents had secondary level of education (51.7%).

Table 1: Socio-demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Age (%)		Marital status (%)		Religion (%)		Occupation (%)		Level of Education (%)	
15-24	24.2	Single	38.2	Christian	83.2	Student	20.2	Non-formal	15.4
25-34	16.6	Married	44.6	Islam	0	Unemployed	29.0	Primary	25.2
35-44	19.9	Divorced	1.3	Traditional	16.8	Civil servant	13.2	Secondary	51.7
45-54	16.1	Separated	4.3	*Total	*100	Self-employed	37.6	Tertiary	7.6
55-64	15.1	Widowed	11.6			*Total	100	*Total	100
>65	8.1	*Total	100						
*Total	100								

* Column percentages. Values may not total 100 due to rounding

Table 2. Weighted Bivariate Associations (at 99% Confidence interval) for Level of Literacy and Socio-cultural determinants of Female Gender Mutilation.

Independent variable	Socio-cultural determinants of FGM						
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
Level of Education							
Non-formal	32.6	23.	28.6	22.8	30.9	29.3	21.6
Primary	24.2	18.8	24.1	19.6	29.7	23.3	17.1
Secondary	19.8	18.7	19.4	17.8	20.6	16.8	11.6
Tertiary	9.3	4.9	5.1	3.2	8.3	2.4	2.1
P value	<0.001	0.003	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001

A= FGM is Rite of initiation into womanhood; B= FGM preserves virginity; C= FGM Enhances fertility; D= FGM signifies purity; E= FGM bridles promiscuity; F= FGM increases sexual pleasure; G= Female Genitalia is dirty

On bivariate association of the weighted whole sample, there was a significant association between the level of literacy and all socio-cultural

determinants of female gender mutilation explored in this study (Table 2).

Table 3. Weighted multivariate associations (at 99% Confidence intervals) for Level of Literacy and Socio-cultural determinants of Female Gender Mutilation

	Independent Variable (Level of Literacy)			
	Non-formal (AOR)	Primary (AOR)	Secondary (AOR)	Tertiary (AOR)
A	1.0(reference)	6.12 ^h (5.07 – 6.88)	2.95 ^{NS} (1.76 – 3.35)	1.12 ^{NS} (0.74 – 2.32)
B	1.0(reference)	5.27 ^{NS} (4.76- 6.26)	1.71 ^{NS} (0.87- 2.01)	0.91 ^{NS} (0.31 – 1.87)
C	1.0(reference)	3.36 ⁱ (2.51 – 4.46)	2.13 ^{NS} (1.31 – 2.14)	1.24 ^{NS} (1.19- 1.60)
D	1.0(reference)	4.14 ^{NS} (3.63 – 5.61)	3.82 ^{NS} (3.06 – 4.90)	2.72 ^{NS} (2.01 – 3.39)
E	1.0(reference)	4.87 ^h (2.23 – 6.33)	3.02 ^j (0.66 – 4.86)	1.13 ^{NS} (0.89 – 2.14)
F	1.0(reference)	2.25 ^{NS} (1.69 – 2.99)	1.16 ^{NS} (0.86 - 1.89)	0.68 ^{NS} (0.24 – 1.02)
G	1.0(reference)	2.18 ^{NS} (1.56 – 2.96)	0.64 ^{NS} (0.41 – 0.99)	0.48 ^{NS} (0.12 – 0.87)

A= FGM is Rite of initiation into womanhood; B= FGM preserves virginity; C= FGM Enhances fertility; D= FGM signifies purity; E= FGM bridles promiscuity; F= FGM increases sexual pleasure; G= Female Genitalia is dirty
h= two tailed P value < 0.0001; i= two tailed p value < 0.001; j= two tailed p value < 0.01; NS= Not significant

DISCUSSION

Literacy rates in Nigeria, especially among the female population, are rising steadily. However, the practice of FGM still goes unmitigated. The socio-cultural determinants of FGM are said to be the most important determinants of FGM²¹⁻²³. Hence, this study was done to identify whether literacy influences the socio-cultural determinants of female gender mutilation (FGM) or not.

This study sought to determine whether level of literacy influences the notion that FGM is a necessary rite of initiation into womanhood. This was statistically significant on bivariate association (p value <0.001; 99% CI). On multivariate analysis,

there was however an association between primary level of education and the same notion [99%CI; AOR = 6.12 (5.07- 6.88); P value <0.0001]. Previous studies have shown that in many tribes who perform FGM around puberty or menarche, it is considered a ‘rite of passage’ symbolizing transition from asexual childhood to sexual adulthood²⁴⁻²⁶.

This study also sought to determine whether level of literacy influences the notion that FGM preserves virginity. This was only statistically significant on bivariate analysis (p = 0.003). Multivariable analysis showed no significance.

The notion that fertility is enhanced by FGM was also analyzed to identify if level of literacy has any influence. It was shown to be statistically significant among those who had primary level of education [99%CI; AOR =3.36 (2.51-4.46); P value<0.001]. In spite of the fact that FGM is known to cause infertility and perinatal mortality²⁷⁻²⁹, FGM is done just before marriage as a ‘fertility rite’^{24, 29}.

This study sought to identify whether level of literacy influences the notion that FGM signifies purity. This was statistically significant on bivariate association only (p<0.001). Multivariable analysis showed no association.

This study sought to determine whether level of literacy influences the notion that FGM bridles promiscuity. It was shown to be statistically significant among the primary [99%CI; AOR=4.87(2.23 – 6.33); p<0.0001] and secondary levels of education [99%CI; AOR=1.16(0.86 -1.89); p value< 0.01]. Usually, the decision for FGM is

made by parents, grandparents, guardians and members of the extended family claiming to act in the girl’s best interest citing reasons such as bridling potential promiscuity²⁵. However, studies have shown that circumcised girls may be promiscuous since they believe they can have sex without losing their virginity²⁹. They also feel they are more matured, desirable and superior to uncircumcised girls²⁹.

This study also sought to determine whether level of literacy influences the belief that FGM increases sexual pleasure. There was no significant association. It is believed that some procedures like infibulation tighten the vagina hence enhancing sexual satisfaction³⁰.

This study sought to determine whether the belief that the female genitalia is dirty necessitating FGM is influenced by literacy level of the participants. There was no significant association.

CONCLUSION

Socio-cultural factors remain the major determinants of Female Gender Mutilation. Increasing female literacy has been said to be instrumental to the decline of FGM. This has occurred over the years; however, the impact of literacy on the determinants of FGM has not been explored over the years. This study has shown that

there is a positive association between level of literacy and some select socio-cultural factors. The implication however is that more female literacy will be instrumental to wiping out the scourge of FGM in Sub-saharan Africa.

Conflict of Interests

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest(s) regarding the publication of this paper.

Authors' contributions	EIA	EDU
Research concept and design	+	
Collection of/and Assembly of data	+	+
Data analysis and interpretation	+	
Writing the Article	+	+
Critical Revision of the Article	+	+
Final Approval of the Article	+	+
Statistical Analysis	+	

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